

DEVELOPMENT AND PROMOTION OF PRODUCTS IN THE COMMODITY MARKET

Mukhitdinova Nigina Isomddinovna
Bukhoro muhandislik-technologysi Institute

Annotation: *This article reflects the transformation of the consumer market in Russia and the formation of strategies for the development of companies at various stages of their existence. Foreign experience is considered, assessment and comparison of sales and promotion strategies with domestic market players is carried out. The most successful strategies in the grocery market have been identified. Conclusions are made about the extremely low implementation of this business tool in domestic companies, arguments are made about the need for massive implementation of strategies by all large and medium-sized manufacturers with a focus on the consumer and fixing their brand in his mind.*

Keywords: *consumer market, development strategy, tactics, companies, transformation, market capacity, planning.*

Introduction

Over the past three decades, the domestic consumer market has come a long way in its development, from the collapse of the command and control system, with a clear and well-organized multi-year planning system, to chaos in the nineties, where none of the domestic companies planned any development strategies and, in principle, they did not could do this due to the collapse of the economy, hyperinflation, the explosive growth of the exchange rate, the constant change in the rules of the game, legislation and an unrealistic tax burden.

Foreign companies, on the contrary, entered the open market, with their sales and marketing systems built for decades, with trained management, with clear development strategies for a long period of time, adequate tactical schemes

for promoting their products, with a competent motivation system that allowed outbidding the best employees in the market. They clearly assessed the size of the market and their opportunities on it, and by the beginning of the 2000s they dominated almost all food categories, with the exception of the segment of perishable food products and products of the essentials category.

The devaluation of the late 1990s allowed domestic producers to become more competitive in the consumer market, primarily in the food market. We started, the first large and structured players appear on the consumer market, WBD, United Confectioners, Cherkizovo, Perekrestok and Magnit appeared in retail. A decade of rapid growth in the consumer market began, which by 2008 amounted to almost 700 billion dollars and was the second largest in Europe and one of the five largest in the world. The next era of stagnation in the 2010s was experienced by far fewer companies, and only those of them survived that clearly defined their development strategy, built sales systems, identified the target consumer, brought successful brands to the market, managed to expand the geography of sales, introduce various types of planning and budgeting . In this article, we will take a closer look at which concepts turned out to be the most effective and in which segments.

Materials and methods

Western multinational companies in their models and development strategies plan their development for a long period of time, in various focus markets for them, with a clear positioning of their products, segmentation by consumers, constant support for marketing across all A[^] and BT channels of promotion. By creating brands, they neutralize some of the overpricing of their popular positions, creating the value of their product for the consumer, they become more financially stable, and due to the vast geography of sales, they almost always dominate the market. I would like to draw attention to the types of strategies of Western companies, product, production, market, resource, marketing

and sales strategy. At the beginning of any entry into a new territory, a thorough analysis and research of the market is carried out, in terms of capacity, potential, the number and financial condition of buyers, the presence of competitors and their strengths and weaknesses, the product portfolio.

Actions for the development of territories and product are similar to military actions, and Western companies resort to the concept of marketing wars in their promotion models. For the first time this term was used by Jack Trout in his book of the same name, where he drew analogies and comparisons of competition with military operations, using the example of military leader Karl von Clausewitz, modeling his principles and rules of military operations in the consumer market. Four strategies have been identified:

- defensive, characteristic of market leaders, with the retention of a certain market share and attacks on themselves, with stopping the threats of competitors;
- offensive, suitable for secondary players, with finding weaknesses in competitors and attacking with all your might along a narrow front;
- flanking, with a new product on the market, entry into a non-competitive field, a change in consumer preferences and paradigm, here you can bring the online market;
- partisan, occupation of a narrow niche and its retention, at any moment the readiness to leave the market with minimal costs.

Due to the active growth of the market, Uzbek manufacturers did not devote enough time to either strategic or tactical aspects, the issues of budgeting, cost reduction and human capital efficiency were also not in the foreground, the rapid growth in sales compensated for everything, there was an era of prosperity, when everyone had enough places. But 2021 came, and then 2022, and many companies simply left the market. In the new paradigm of the decade of recession, only the most efficient ones could hold on, who had introduced the whole range of tools for the strategic development of their enterprises in advance, were clearly

positioned in the minds of the consumer, identified and satisfied his needs with their product, managed to build a sales system in vast territories, introduced direct sales teams , actively worked with a network distribution channel, supported their product with advertising and other marketing tools, implemented various types of cost and profit budget control, and were able to form teams of effective managers.

Literature review

Domestic leaders would have come in very handy with books that would help them comprehend the whole picture of the market and be useful in structuring and developing their companies for a long period of time, in addition to the previously mentioned Jack Trout with "Marketing Wars", I would like to note Philip Kotler and "Fundamentals of Marketing" , where all marketing tools at all times of human civilization are substantively and in detail considered and analyzed, he was the first to describe marketing concepts, from focusing on a product to introducing social and ethical marketing. Yitzhak Adizes and his work "The Life Cycle of Corporations" fully revealed the stages of development and life of all companies in the world and proposed a list of actions for their continuous development. John King "The Leader and the Tribe", everything you need to know about building a corporate culture and achieving the intended team goals, Brian Tracy and his publications "How the Best Manage", "Management" and others dedicated to management and management, Nassim Nicole Taleb with his book "Antifragile" described in detail the transition from chaos to structuring. Neil Eyar, Ryan Hoover "Hooked"

“Marketing Hack” by Phil Barden, Byron Sharp “How Brands Grow”, these publications analyze in detail, with a large number of examples from the real sector of the economy, due to which the consumer makes purchase decisions, how to identify the need and satisfy it and stay in the mind with own product, considered a huge number of promotion models, proposed steps for the successful building of brands. "The Game to Win" by Alan Lafley, CEO of Procter and

Gamble, in collaboration with Roger Martin, created one of the best scientific and practical works on the formation of strategies on the example of the world's leading companies, and Thomas T.Nera with his work "Strategy and Tactics of Pricing » discussed in detail the issues of this aspect in terms of price and costs. Among domestic authors, I would like to single out Igor Lipsits “Marketing for Top Managers”.

Results

The retail trade turnover in January-March 2022 reached 59 057.3 billion soums and increased by 10.8% compared to the same period in 2021, and the turnover of large enterprises amounted to 13 971.2 billion soums (growth rate - 154.2%), and small businesses and private entrepreneurship – 45 086.1 billion soums (growth rate - 102.0%), unorganized trade amounted to 5 283.2 billion soums (growth rate - 111.2%).

Structure of retail trade turnover and growth rates, in %

Turnover of unorganized trade

(billion soums)

Наиболее высокий удельный вес в общем объеме розничного товарооборота отмечен в г.Ташкент и он составил 23,7 %, Ташкентской – 11,0 %, Самаркандской – 8,2 %, Ферганской – 7,9 % и Андижанской – 7,4 % областях. Наиболее низкий удельный вес зафиксирован в Сырдарьинской области – 1,6 % и Республике Каракалпакстан –3,3 %.

Discussion

As we discussed earlier, perishable food producers turned out to be the most successful, they simply did not have competitors in the form of foreign structured companies. And many of them have not yet implemented the tools of strategic planning and tactically defined organizational and marketing models. Here, local, very meager producers began to crowd them out, bakeries, farm butcher shops, small confectionery breweries are actively developing, which are already crowding out “foreigners”. A boom in food products with a short shelf life has begun in the country, a culture of consumption has grown, this was caught by small producers who have become unable to get on the shelf in the network and have begun to actively enter the market, entire networks of specialized stores of this format are appearing. There is an active transformation of the market from long-term products to short-term and online trends - trade here is also not so noticeable, you want to choose hot bread, good meat, fresh milk and vegetables yourself. And this trend will continue in the coming years.

The market for cosmetic products is developing quite extraordinary: firstly, there is a lot of diverse information about cosmetic products that helps shape the opinion of consumers, and secondly, it must be taken into account that beauty products do not belong to the group of essential goods.

According to the results of marketing research by GfK, in 2020, the cosmetics market is experiencing a steady growth in turnover through the most popular distribution channels through the discounter trade format.

It is necessary to consider and adapt to modern conditions the factors that have influenced the dynamic market situation of the channels for promoting cosmetic products in retail. The trends that characterize the development of the market of cosmetic products include such important factors as the reduction of expenses for the purchase of perfumery products, the volume of which in previous years occupied almost a third of the market in monetary terms; as well as the bulk of sales flowed from specialized perfume stores in the "discounter at home" format and online stores.

An analysis of the Uzbek distribution channels of the cosmetics market revealed the following possible innovative solutions that will allow them to take the lead in the market in the future:

- introduction of innovative ingredients into formulations that improve the qualitative composition of cosmetic products;
- increasing the degree of satisfaction of consumer expectations;
- price advantages compared to competitors with the same quality of cosmetics;
- maintaining a wide product range.

However, the competitive situation in the cosmetics market can change very quickly, so product distribution channels must be constantly monitored and marketing communications adapted to consumer needs and needs.

To do this, it is enough to conduct a small in-depth marketing research, which will identify opportunities for more effective communication with

consumers.

Conclusion

Companies currently operating in segments with a short shelf life for successful development for a long period of time need to develop high-quality development strategies in the near future, with a focus on the consumer and his needs, actively develop and support their brands with marketing and position it in the mind of the consumer as useful product in its market segment.

For sales growth, it is necessary to create exclusive sales teams, introduce motivation and control systems and manage the shelf space and further the entire sales system to the end consumer, and constantly update the assortment. It is required to expand the geography of sales, introduce uniform corporate standards in all territories, create and improve the quality of personnel through continuous training.

In addition to profit, the main performance indicators should be an increase in market share, an increase in consumer loyalty, quantitative distribution, coverage quality, work with the logistics component, the level of customer service, labor productivity, capacity planning, description and implementation of business process management, quality management, creation of a personnel reserve, IT service, developed information and technological base, constant control of the marketing strategy and budget, its own retail distribution channel.

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